

Социальный заказ на формирование просоциальности российских студентов социономических направлений подготовки: от личностных качеств к профессиональным компетенциям

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Актуальность обращения к проблеме формирования просоциальных установок поведения студенческой молодежи связана с необходимостью гармонизации межличностных отношений в современном российском обществе. Особое внимание, уделяемое российским высшим учебным заведениям, связано с тем, что вузовская среда является не только образовательным, но и социокультурным пространством, в котором осуществляется социализация молодежи. Именно выпускники вузов, обучавшиеся на социономических направлениях подготовки, в будущем и будут являться тем актором выстраивания доброжелательных отношений и солидарных ценностей в российском обществе.

Цель исследования – исследование выработки социального заказа на формирование просоциальности студентов российских вузов, обучающихся на социономических направлениях подготовки и его нормативное оформление.

Материалы и методы. Идентификация социального заказа на формирование просоциальности студентов, обучающихся на социономических направлениях подготовки, и его анализ осуществлялась на основе рассмотрения нормативных документов определяющих требования к результатам освоения основных образовательных программ (образовательные стандарты) и нормативные документы, определяющие требования к квалификации специалиста, необходимой ему для выполнения определенной трудовой функции (профессиональные стандарты). Определение указанных групп документов в качестве источниковой основы исследования позволяет рассмотреть социальный заказ как двунаправленный процесс с одной стороны – от системы высшего профессионального образования, и от потенциальных работодателей – с другой.

Результаты. Установлено, что просоциальность входит в число базовых личностных качеств студенческой молодежи, и на этой основе возможно формирование просоциальных профессиональных компетенций, в первую очередь у будущих специалистов, которые посвятят свою жизнь социономическим профессиям. Анализ образовательных стандартов социономических направлений подготовки и профессиональных стандартов социономических профессий позволил выявить наличие просоциального сегмента в их профессиограмме.

Заключение. Анализ работ и нормативных документов, определяющих требования к профессиональной подготовке специалистов в социономической сфере, позволил сделать наблюдение о том, что формирование просоциальных качеств студентов является точкой пересечения потребностей общества в гармонизации межличностных отношений, запроса государства и профессионального сообщества на подготовку специалиста, успешно реализующего ценности просоциальности в своей работе.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

просоциальность, высшее профессиональное образование, социономические направления подготовки, студенческая молодежь, качества личности, профессиональные компетенции

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Social mandate for forming prosociality in Russian students of socio-economic educational profile: from personal qualities to professional competencies

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of addressing the problem of forming prosocial attitudes in student behaviour is connected with the need to harmonise interpersonal relations in modern Russian society. The special attention paid to Russian higher education institutions is explained by the fact that the university environment is not only an educational but also a sociocultural space where young people get socialised. It is the graduates of socio-economic training profile at higher education institutions that will become the actors building friendly relations and promoting solidarity values in Russian society in the future.

The aim of the study is to explore the issues of framing the social mandate for the formation of prosociality in students of Russian universities majoring in socio-economic areas, and its regulatory patternisation.

Materials and methods. The identification of the social mandate for the formation of prosociality in socio-economic-profile students and its analysis was carried out on the basis of the regulatory documents defining the requirements for the results of mastering the basic educational programmes (educational standards) and the regulatory documents defining the requirements for a specialist's qualification necessary for performing a certain job function (professional standards). The specification of these groups of documents as a source basis for the research makes it possible to consider the social mandate as a bidirectional process – the system of higher professional education, on the one hand, and potential employers, on the other hand.

Results. It was established that prosociality is one of the basic personal qualities of students; therefore, it is possible to form prosocial professional competencies on this basis – primarily, in future specialists who will devote their lives to socio-economic professions. The analysis of the educational standards in socio-economic training areas as well as the professional standards in socio-economic professions made it possible to reveal a prosocial segment in their job profile diagram.

Conclusion. The analysis of works and regulatory documents defining the requirements for professional training of socio-economic-sphere specialists made it possible to conclude that the formation of students' prosocial qualities is the point of intersection of social needs towards the harmonisation of interpersonal relations, and the state's and professional community's mandate to train specialists successfully realising the prosociality values in their work.

KEYWORDS

prosociality, higher professional education, socio-economic areas of training, students, personal qualities, professional competencies

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INTRODUCTION

The formation of sociality and corresponding socially significant attitudes in university education of young people is reflected at the international level in UNESCO's documents and is considered a foundation for achieving peace and sustainable development. In confirmation of this, one can cite the statement of S. Giannini, Deputy of UNESCO's Assistant Director-General for Education: "Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) plays a pivotal role in empowering individuals with the knowledge, skills and values necessary to act as catalysts for positive change" [1, p. 8].

In the Russian educational system, the relevance of studying the university segment in the process of formation of young people's prosocial behaviour attitudes is connected with the need to adapt the paradigm of helping behaviour to the conditions of national higher education. It seems obvious that it is the higher school that is the space for the generation of new – in this case, prosocial – meanings and their extension to all strata of modern society. Students, while studying at universities, are in the phase of intensive socialisation associated with mastering professional competencies and cultivating the related moral and ethical norms of a certain professional community. Students, being of legal age and having already acquired socialisation skills, not only can assimilate the prosociality values but also take an active part in the formation of the national model of prosocial society. They are not only consumers of the helping behaviour ideas but also prosociality actors – not only in the format of individual action but also within the framework of public institutions that implement prosocial projects on a voluntary basis.

The scholarly interest in discussing the problem of the development of prosocial professional education has become consistent in modern Russian psychological and pedagogical discourse. This represents a reflection of public expectations for the humanisation of higher education [2, p. 828] (to a greater extent, pedagogical education [3] which, according to some researchers, is "a source of inspiration for regaining human values" [4]), especially as concerns future specialists working in the "human-to-human" sphere, i.e., socioeconomic professional sphere (humanisation of higher education is also a trend for its areas such as business education [5, p. 544], considering the impact of religious factors [6, p. 7]).

The scholars who consider the prosociality formation problem in modern education produce scientific results that point to the connection between the efficient performance of professional duties by specialists of socioeconomic professions and the presence of helping personal qualities; therefore, they propose to directly include the formation of prosocial motivation in job profile diagrams of socioeconomic professions.

Such helping personal qualities include, in the first place, empathy, benevolence, social responsibility, emotional intelligence, tolerance (including in relation to other nations [7, p. 76]), altruism, compassion, conscientiousness and justice. Scientists also find manifestations of prosocial qualities in individuals' human values, environmental friendliness, respect for national traditions, and loyalty to national and state interests [7, p. 76].

Analysing the materials on different regions of Russia, Russian researchers attempted to assess the presence of prosociality in students and revealed their readiness to follow helping strategies when realising professional competencies in the future. For instance, Kalinina's and Guseva's study convincingly demonstrates the need to work on the formation of university students' prosociality [8, p. 41]. As shown by the survey undertaken by these authors in 2011, 2015–2017 and 2020–2022, the leading motives in students who mastered socioeconomic specialties and training areas were associated with external drivers showing the impact of various factors of the learners' environment [8, p. 41].

At the same time, the researchers found out that young people show certain progress in the development of various aspects of prosociality. This process slows down by the end of adolescence and then is activated after 25–26 years of age [7, p. 76].

Scientists also relate the process of formation of students' civic position and social activity with prosocial and personal qualities: "The formation of civic position and social activity is specific of young people having such individual characteristics as humanism, environmental friendliness and respect for national traditions. In addition, such young people are more tolerant towards other nations and show loyalty to national and state interests" [7, p. 76] [7, p. 76]. The same opinion was

expressed by Lyubtsova describing the value orientations of modern young people in the context of the formation of prosocial behaviour.

In the course of a large-scale survey exploring the prosocial activity of students held in 2021 and covering universities and colleges of all federal districts of the Russian Federation, national scholars made an interesting observation: "The motivation of students' prosocial activity quite clearly characterises the extent of actualisation of their prosociality in the regions as one of the important social processes" [9 p. 12].

Students' prosocial attitudes and relevant behaviour have been studied by scholars with the coverage of different training areas. In particular, the survey of pedagogical-profile students from the universities of Saransk, Ivanovo, Nizhny Novgorod, Astrakhan, St. Petersburg and Leningrad Region, Moscow and Moscow Region revealed that "the dominant prosocial tendency of future teachers is manifested in compliant, prompt and anonymous prosocial behaviour; care of others serves as a predominant value; helping friends characterises their altruistic inclinations" [10, p. 13].

Some studies of prosocial motivation were also undertaken in relation to students of technical universities. Socially active students of technical universities taking an active part in extracurricular activities and those of public organisations demonstrate an active life position, interact with other people, and inspire esteem and sympathy [11, p. 206]. Their value-based worldview is dominated by universal, personal and social values [11, p. 209].

The problems of the formation of prosocial attitudes are also considered by national researchers for higher educational establishments in the sphere of emergency response. The survey of prosocial activity of cadets of Ivanovo Fire and Rescue Academy under the State Fire-Fighting Service of the Ministry of the Russian Federation for Civil Defence, Emergencies and Elimination of Consequences of Natural Disasters revealed that "the future firefighters' dominant prosocial tendency is emergency-based prosocial behaviour; people's safety and care for humans are prevailing values; their altruistic inclinations are based on helping friends and strangers" [12, p. 78].

The national experience of implementing prosocial technologies in the process of education and character-building is also described in the professional press. For instance, the 2017–2018 study by Toropov involving Kaliningrad students revealed that the idea of prosocial education is supported by parents and teachers; moreover, the introduction of social assistance technology made it possible to record positive dynamics of university students' prosocial competence [13, p. 98].

In addition, some early works of the authors' team present the results of exploring the formation of university students' prosocial attitudes and behaviours. For instance, earlier, the authors shared with the scientific community their experience of testing the original course "Introduction to prosocial pedagogical activity" at Belgorod State National Research University. In addition, the research conducted among the students of the Pedagogical Institute under Belgorod State National Research University revealed the presence of 16 prosocial competencies [14, p. 29]. It was shown that the core of the prosocial model of pedagogical education is formed by several competencies: regulatory ("ability to manage relationships and conflicts"), affective ("benevolence, beneficence"), and stimulating ("ability to develop the capabilities of others") [14, p. 16]. The scientific definition of "individual's prosocial attitude" was remastered into the aspect of teachers' professional competence; it was proposed to consider prosocial competencies as "inclusive" and able to reconcile the universal soft skills formed throughout one's life [15, p. 1] – in practical activity [17, p. 529] and with the help of active teaching methods [16, p. 122] that are important in professional training [18, p. 424] – with a high level of interpersonal communicative skills [19, p. 104] tending to self-efficacy [20] and self-development [21, p. 13]) and general/professional hard skills developed in practical activity [22], including those developed in the sphere of students' assistance to teachers [23, p. 879], with regard for individual skills [24, p. 73] that are innovative in nature [25, p. 103] and are largely based on digital literacy [26, p. 167]) of future educators in the conditions of higher pedagogical education.

Although the world scientific community has undertaken a lot of studies exploring the formation of young people's prosociality, the authors of the present research consider the extent of elaboration of the addressed issue to be insufficient – as concerns the study of the relevant social mandate and its regulatory formulation towards the formation of prosociality among Russian university students mastering socionomic areas.

The aim of the article is to explore the issues of framing the social mandate for the formation of prosociality in students of Russian universities studying socioeconomic areas, and its regulatory patternisation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodological basis of the research is grounded on the idea of interdependence of social needs and due development of the educational system, particularly, higher professional education. The public need for the harmonisation of interpersonal relations exists, on the one hand, as a socially declared value, and, on the other hand, as a practical activity of public institutions towards creating new and optimising the existing social mechanisms regulating social behaviour. The institutional residents engaged in the verification and documenting of public needs in the sphere of higher professional education in the Russian Federation are represented by public authorities and professional associations. In this regard, their activities result in the development of state educational and professional standards.

The methodological basis of the research is rooted in the principles of the anthropological approach to exploring the problems of prosocial education development. The principles of pedagogical anthropology are considered by modern Russian scientists as a core of effective tools for studying the problems of education, treating the above as a basic property of human existence [27, p. 320]. The present study, with its anthropological orientation at scientific reflection, made it possible to comprehensively assess the presence of prosociality in students.

The following scientific research methods were used in the work. The textological analysis of documents made it possible to identify the existence of competencies in the regulatory and methodological support, to be used for the formation of prosociality in the general education process of higher school.

The use of the comparison method made it possible to establish the presence of competencies in the current Russian state standards and professional standards of education, that are related to the formation of prosociality in future specialists.

The source base of the present study is represented by regulatory methodological documents setting the state policy of the Russian Federation in the field of higher education – educational state standards for different levels of training (regulatory socioeconomic training areas), and professional standards.

The involved regulatory materials and their analysis made it possible to form wide-ranging judgements on the existence of a social mandate in Russia for the formation of prosocial competencies among students of Russian universities.

RESULTS

In Russia, the social mandate for the formation of prosocial attitudes is reflected in the most general form in the provisions of the federal law "On Education in the Russian Federation" [28]. As is known, it defines the category of "education" as "the activity aimed at the development of a personality ... in the interests of the individual, the family, the society and the state, for the formation of students' patriotism, civic consciousness, respect for the memory of the native land defenders and the feats of the Heroes of the Fatherland, ... reciprocal respect, careful attitude towards the cultural heritage and traditions of the multiple nations of the Russian Federation, the country's nature and environment" [28]. This law also defines the principles of the state policy in the field of education. Among them is "the humanistic nature of education in accordance with Russian traditional spiritual and moral values, the priority of human life and health, rights and freedoms, free development of the individual; nurturing mutual respect, diligence, civic consciousness, patriotism, commitment, legal culture, respect for nature and the environment, and rational use of natural resources" [28]. Obviously, this principle is inherently prosocial.

This humanistic principle in the aspect of education is enshrined in basic provisions of state educational standards for socio-economic areas of training and professional standards. In particular, the federal state standard of higher education for the Bachelor's degree in profile 37.03.01 Psychology assumes the graduates' achievement of the professional activity goals in remedial, rehabilitation and counselling areas [29]. The Bachelor's degree programme should include the following general professional competencies: psychological intervention (GPC-4. Able to use the basic forms of psychological assistance for handling specific problems of individuals, population groups and (or) institutions, including persons with disabilities, and for the organisation of inclusive education; GPC-5. Able to perform organisational and technical work involving the implementation of specific measures of preventive, developmental, remedial or rehabilitative nature) [29]. One of the professional activity areas of graduates who have mastered the Bachelor's degree programme in profile 39.03.02 Social Work is, as a matter of fact, prosocial activity, namely, social services and social protection of the population [30].

The Bachelor's degree programme in profile 44.03.01 Pedagogical Education provides for the formation of prosocial competencies in graduates upon successful completion of the programme: organisation of joint and individual educational and character-building activities, including for learners with special education needs (GPC-3), creating a due educative environment; spiritual and moral education of students based on traditional national values (GPC-4); using beneficial psychological and pedagogical technologies in professional activities that are necessary for the individualisation of training, development and education, including for students with special education needs (GPC-6) [31].

Graduates of the Bachelor's degree programme in profiles 44.03.02 Psychological and Pedagogical Education [32] and 44.03.05 Pedagogical Education (envisaging two training profiles) should use helping strategies in their professional activity [33]. They should be able to use in their professional activity, among other general professional competencies, psychological and pedagogical technologies necessary for the individualisation of training, due development and character-building, which also concerns students with special educational needs (GPC-6) [33]. This also applies to graduates of the Bachelor's degree programme in profile 44.03.03 Special (Defectologic) Education who are supposed to demonstrate the competence of identifying and managing learning difficulties experienced by students with special education needs (GPC-6) [34]. The last mentioned competence should be realised as well by graduates of the Bachelor's degree programme 44.03.04 in the profile Vocational Training (by area) [35].

As for the schooling level of Master degree graduates, the following training programmes are envisaged by the current Russian state educational standards specifying the scope of training under the relevant curricula: 44.04.01 Pedagogical Education [36], 44.04.02 Psychological and Pedagogical Education [37], 44.04.03 Special (Defectologic) Education [38], 44.04.04 Vocational Education (by area) [39], which standards are aimed at implementing helping activity strategies.

The presence and maturity of prosocial competencies in prospective specialists seem important and relevant for potential employers. In the context of the present research, the prosocial competence requirements for specialists, set by the developers of professional standards for socio-economic professions, can be considered in two aspects. Firstly, they can be treated as "hard competencies" that characterise the efficiency of specialists who cope with their professional duties related to interacting with people and helping them. Secondly, they can be regarded as "soft competencies": their maturity, shown by socio-economic professionals, is deemed to be a necessary continuation of their professional competencies.

The professional standard of a pedagogue is indicative in this regard: describing the function "Educational Activity", it declares, as a labour action, "assistance and support in organising the activity of students' self-governing bodies"; moreover, it includes the ability to "protect the learners' dignity and interests, help children to build necessary skills in conflict situations and/or unfavourable conditions". Realising the labour function "Developing Activities", the teacher is supposed to perform in fact two actions. The first one is "Mastering and application of psychological and pedagogical technologies (inclusive ones among them) necessary for targeted work with different student bodies: gifted children, socially vulnerable children, children in difficult life situations, migrant children, orphans, children with special educational needs (autistic children, children with attention deficit disorder and hyperactive children), children with disabilities, children with deviant behaviour, and addicted children". The second one is "Targeted assistance to learners". The successful realisation of

these functions is possible with the developed ability to “develop and implement individual education routes, individual development programmes and individually oriented educational programmes with regard for the learners’ personal and age-specific characteristics”.

The module “Subject Teaching. Mathematics” contains two positions that can be attributed to prosocial ones: “assisting in preparing students for the participation in mathematical contests, competitions, research projects, brain marathons, chess tournaments and student conferences”, and the ability to “provide assistance to students who have not mastered the necessary material (from the course of mathematics) – in the form of offered special assignments and individual counselling (including distance guidance). This also assumes step-by-step control of completion of the assigned tasks, with resorting to the assistance of other teachers, in particular, tutors, if necessary” [40].

Professional psychologists are required to have an extensive set of prosocial skills. In particular, the professional standard “Pedagogue-psychologist (psychologist in the sphere of education)” defines the goal of the professional activity type entitled “Psychological and pedagogical support of the educational process” as follows: “Psychological and pedagogical assistance to persons with disabilities experiencing difficulties in mastering basic general education programmes, development and adaptation, including underage students who are recognised, in cases and in the manner prescribed by the criminal procedure legislation, as suspects, accused parties or defendants on a criminal case, or as victims or witnesses of an offence” [41].

When realising the job function “Psychological expertise (assessment) of comfort and safety of the educational environment”, the teacher-psychologist is supposed to demonstrate the ability to “develop and implement programmes envisaging psychological support of innovative processes in the educational organisation, including programmes to support students’ associations and student self-governance”.

The labour function “Psychological education of training process participants” includes the realisation of the following labour action: “Informing about the factors hindering personal development of children, trainees and students and on the measures aimed to provide them with various types of psychological assistance”.

To perform the labour function “Psychological prevention (professional activity aimed at preserving and strengthening the learners’ psychological health in the process of education and character-building at educational organisations)”, a specialist should be able to “plan and organise the work towards preventing possible problems in students’ mental and personal development, including in socially vulnerable learners and those facing difficult life situations” and “develop recommendations for teachers, parents, tutors and other members of educational organisations towards assisting students in adaptation, pre-crisis and crisis periods” [41].

The job profile diagram of a social-sphere psychologist is also inherently prosocial since it supposes social and psychological support to the population. The purpose of this type of activity is defined as “improving people’s mental state, recovering the individuals’ and social groups’ ability to adapt to life circumstances; prevention and psychological correction of negative social manifestations in people’s behaviour”.

The skills necessary for the successful achievement of this goal are also prosocial. The realisation of the labour function “Psychological and socio-psychological support of citizens and social groups” presupposes the ability “to provide psychological support to people towards helping them to overcome difficult life situations”. Psychological assistance to families with children and their socio-psychological support is possible if the specialist can “select effective forms and methods of psychological assistance to families with children in accordance with the set tasks” and is skilled in the methods of “individualised psychological assistance to families in difficult life situations”.

Psychological assistance to members of social-sphere institutions and organisations also supposes the knowledge and skills related to rendering psychological assistance to the staff thereof [42].

Among the school specialists dealing with character-building are the director's advisor on education and interaction with children’s public associations, social pedagogue, senior youth leader, organising teacher and tutor; the greatest prosocial segment is represented in the job profile diagram of a social pedagogue.

The social pedagogue's professional activity within the framework of the labour function "Planning the measures of social and pedagogical support of learners in the process of socialisation" is possible if the pedagogue has due skills enabling him/her to outline a necessary set of measures for students' social and pedagogical support and provide first aid to them. In turn, these skills, when mature, suppose that the social pedagogue is aware of the forms and methods of the learners' socio-pedagogical support in the process of education and in difficult life situations.

The organisation of the learners' socio-pedagogical support in the process of socialisation includes: firstly, the skills to "effectuate the measures of socio-pedagogical support to students in the assimilation of educational programmes", to "apply pedagogical support technologies for students' social initiatives" and "engage in targeted socio-pedagogical support of learners facing difficult life situations with regard for the specifics of their social problems"; secondly, the knowledge of mechanisms and technologies of students' socio-pedagogical support in helping them to master educational programmes, designing individual routes, in situations of self-identification as well as in difficult and socially dangerous life situations.

The ability to render organisational, methodological and socio-pedagogical support to students is coupled in the professional standard with the ability to develop information and methodological materials for socio-pedagogical support programmes, to provide students with organisational and pedagogical support in building social relationships and adapting to new life situations; to offer socio-pedagogical support of orphans and learners left without parental care. These skills in turn are based on the knowledge of approaches to the methodological support of programmes, mechanisms of programmatic and methodological social partnership of socialisation institutions, forms and methods of control, methods of diagnosing and analysing the outcomes of programmes and activities involving social and pedagogical support of students.

The prosocial component in the job profile diagram of the organising teacher and tutor is realised through advisory assistance. The organising teacher should be able to "render consultative assistance to students in terms of self-identification, choice of the sphere of future professional activity" and "provide pedagogical support of students' public associations". For this purpose, he/she should know the "technologies of students' pedagogical support in pursuing their individual routes in collective activities".

The tutor, in the process of pedagogical support of students, including those with disabilities, when realising individual educational routes and projects, should demonstrate the ability "to secure the learners' pedagogical support upon the manifestation of their educational needs and interests", "to assist students in the formation of their individual educational needs", "to render advisory support to students in the process of their professional self-identification", "to apply pedagogical support technologies to students upon their development of due individual educational paths and projects", "to provide pedagogical support for students' educational initiatives and the implementation of their individual projects". When realising the labour function "Organisation of educational environment for the realisation by students, including those with disabilities, of individual educational paths and projects", the tutor should be able to "assist the family in building the due family educational environment with a view to support students in mastering individual study plans and adapted educational programmes" and "render consultative support to students and parents in the creation of due conditions for mastering individual curricula and adapted educational programmes".

The pedagogues working in the position of director's advisor for education and interaction with children's public associations and the position of senior youth leader should comply in their professional activities with the helping paradigm in supporting school self-governance and children's public organisations. In particular, the director's advisor for education and interaction with children's public associations should "promote the due functioning of the student self-governance system and stimulate the development of new forms of student self-governance" and be able to "develop plans and programmes for organising activities aimed at supporting students in difficult life situations".

The job duties of the senior youth leader include the realisation of three prosocial labour functions: "Pedagogical support in the institution of public associations", "Pedagogical support of children's public associations' activities" and "Development of student self-governance on the basis of social institutions' social partnership". The necessary skills required for the successful realisation of the above functions include: "to provide pedagogical support of children's initiatives", "to provide pedagogical support of learners in the formation of their creative public associations and self-

governing bodies”, “to provide pedagogical support of students in the process of self-identification within the framework of collective activity programmes”, “to organise support for children’s social projects on the basis of the social partnership of socialisation-purpose institutions”, “to promote support for activities of children’s associations in the society, to motivate specialists of different profiles to work with children and teenagers”. At the same time, the youth leader needs to know the theory and methodology of pedagogical support for activities of children’s public organisations, movements, and associations, as well as the ways of pedagogical support for participation of volunteers in the development of children’s public organisations [43].

The requirements for pedagogues working in the system of supplementary education also include a prosocial component. In particular, the professional standard “Supplementary education teacher” enshrines the following general/professional prosocial skills: “to use various means of pedagogical support to students” and “to use various means of pedagogical support for learners experiencing communication difficulties” [44]. The professional standard “Specialist working with young people” specifies the following generalised prosocial competencies: “development of mechanisms for targeted assistance to young people facing difficult life situations and young people in need of special care from the state” [45].

DISCUSSION

The problem of students’ prosociality falls within the research area of professional educators (who study its various aspects, including the problem of equality and justice in the issues of subsequent remuneration of university graduates, with a view to exclude any marginalisation [5, p. 544]. The research gives the essential characteristics of future teachers’ competence model [14, p. 11], such as teamwork, emotional intelligence [17, p. 121], the fundamental role of education in expanding the opportunities for further employment [18, p. 424]), the role of psychologists (who consider prosociality in the context of the development of a person’s emotional intelligence) [4], the relationship between education, religious and moral values [6], the development of a person’s prosocial attitudes [8, p. 35], as well as the forms of personal activity [10, p. 10], students’ psychological characteristics [11, p. 206]), the role of sociologists (studying the motivation of prosocial activity) [9, p. 5], technologies of prosocial education [13, p. 98], the efficiency of interpersonal communication skills for the formation of a friendly atmosphere in a team [25, p. 103], anthropologisation of approaches to continuing professional education [27, p. 320]). The authors of numerous studies agree that prosociality is one of the priority values of Russian students; therefore, the formation of behavioural prosocial attitudes in the student environment can take place on the basis of a fundamental platform of personal qualities shaped in young people by the time they enter higher educational establishments [7, p. 79]. National scholars’ research interest in diagnosing students’ prosocial personal qualities and the process of their formation can be considered one of the indicators of the need existing in Russian society to harmonise interpersonal relations through the introduction of a helping paradigm.

The regulatory form of the social mandate is represented in the system of statutory documents defining the content of education (educational standards) and requirements for the qualification of a specialist (professional standards). It can be stated, relative to socionomic professions selected as the subject of the present study, that prosocial qualities in both types of documents are embedded in the job profile diagram. The presence of the concepts “help” and “support” in the texts of the educational and professional standards is indicative, as concerns the description of competencies and labour functions. In this regard, there are grounds to assert that, firstly, there exists a public need for prosociality and, secondly, one can talk of the state mandate for the inclusion of helping technologies in the training of socionomic professionals.

CONCLUSION

The problem of harmonisation of interpersonal relations is relevant for modern Russia, and the search for ways to work it up is in the focus of state authorities, public organisations and the scientific community. One of the established models of such harmonisation is prosocial. The successful realisation of this model of social relations is possible only in the presence of prosocial behaviour attitudes formed in the population of the country.

In this regard, higher education institutions can certainly be regarded as actors in this process. Students represent the human resource that ensures the due transmission of values in everyday life and subsequent professional activities. As to socio-economic professions, they are, in the first place, a space for the formation of prosociality as a personal quality and, most importantly, as a professional competence. Commitment to helping another person in this professional field becomes an ability and a skill enabling one to do this with the best result and with the least damage to the actor's psychological health.

The studies by the national authors convincingly testify to the following tendencies: firstly, the problem of forming prosocial qualities in students of Russian higher education institutions is in the interdisciplinary field of view; secondly, prosociality is a quality socially approved by modern Russian students, which enables one to make optimistic forecasts on the prospects of its formation in the youth environment; thirdly, the above observations indicate the presence of a demand for prosociality in modern Russian society, primarily, in the higher professional education system. This demand resonates with the state, educational institutions and the professional community, which, in turn, points to the existence of a synergistic effect in the process of formation of students' prosociality. Moreover, as shown by the analysis of educational and professional standards, potential employers demonstrate a pronounced interest in the presence of prosocial qualities – as a segment of professional competence – in a specialist working in the socio-economic sphere.

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ЛИТЕРАТУРА

1. Education for sustainable development: a roadmap (2022). Corporate author: UNESCO [66654]. Paris 07 SP, France. – Document code: 10.54675/YFRE1448, 66 p. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374802>
2. Novikova N. V., Nechaeva T. Yu., Avezova, Dubrovina I. A. The humanization of medical education: publication review. *Problems of Social Hygiene Public and History of Medicine*. 2024. July. № 32 (4). Pp. 828-832. <https://doi.org/10.32687/0869-866X-2024-32-4-828-832>
3. Soares F., Lopes A. Fostering humanization in education: a scoping review on mindfulness and teacher education. *Frontiers in Education*. 2024. № 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1373500>
4. Rodriguez M.E., Fortunato I. Paulo Friere's contributions to 21st century teacher education: Inspirations for (re)discovering humanization. *Policy Futures in Education*. 2025. February. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14782103251323403>
5. Dorathy W.C., Sam-Eleyi F.O. Workplace Humanization and Job Effectiveness of Business Education Graduates in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. *Journal of Advances in Education and Philosophy*. 2024. № 8 (09). Pp. 544-551. <https://doi.org/10.36348/jaep.2024.v08i09.004>
6. Azuakor P.O. The role of religion (Islam and Christianity) and education for humanization: Nigeria in perspective. *Integrity Journal of Arts and Humanities*. 2023. № 4 (1). Pp. 7-15. <https://doi.org/10.31248/IJAH2022.065>
7. Любцова А. В. Ценностные ориентиры современной молодежи в контексте формирования просоциального поведения // *Российский психологический журнал*. 2020. Т.17. №4. С. 65-79.
8. Калинина Т. В., Гусева Н. В. Формирование просоциального поведения в контексте профессиональной подготовки студентов помогающих специальностей и направлений обучения // *Социально-психологические проблемы просоциального поведения современного поколения детей и молодежи. Материалы II Всероссийской научно-практической конференции с международным участием. Симферополь: ООО «Издательство Типография "Ариал"». С. 35-44.*
9. Шмелева Е. А., Басимов М. М., Кисляков П. А., Константинова Н. П. Психологические предпосылки мотивации просоциальной активности студенческой молодежи // *Ученые записки Российского государственного социального университета*. 2021. Т. 20. № 1 (158). С. 5-15.
10. Шмелева Е. А., Кисляков П. А., Стародубцева Л. В., Прияткина Н. Ю. Просоциальная активность будущих педагогов // *Вестник Мининского университета*. 2021. Т. 9. № 4. С. 1-20.

11. Тарасова Е. О., Юрьев К. В. Социально-психологический портрет социально активного студента технического вуза // Вестник Самарского государственного технического университета. Серия: Психолого-педагогические науки. 2015. Том 12. № 1. С. 206-210.
12. Шмелева Е. А., Океанская Ж. Л., Кисляков П. А. Методика изучения просоциальной активности обучающихся образовательных организаций МЧС России // Пожарная и аварийная безопасность. 2020. № 3 (18). - С. 70-81.
13. Торопов П. Б. Результат педагогического эксперимента: социальное содействие как технология просоциального образования // Известия Балтийской государственной академии рыбопромышленного флота. 2018. № 1 (43). С. 98-103.
14. Ерошенкова Е. И., Шаповалова И. С., Карабутова Е. А., Анохина С. В., Мирошникова О. С. Просоциальная компетентностная модель будущего педагога // Образование и наука. 2022. Т. 24. № 2. С. 11-47. <https://doi.org/10.17853/1994-5639-2022-2-11-47>
15. Bhaskar C. V., Priyadharshini P. R. S., Govindharaj P., Sam D Pr. The role of group projects in enhancing soft skills. Humanities and Social Sciences Communications 12(1). April 2025. Pp. 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-025-04807-x>
16. Nikitina E. A., Budovskaya I. V. The empirical research of development features of students' soft-skills. Proceedings of the Southwest State University Series Linguistics and Pedagogy. 2025. № 14 (4). Pp. 121-131. <https://doi.org/10.21869/2223-151X-2024-14-4-121-131>
17. Ayyadurai S., Akkara Joy S., Edapallikunnel J.J., Joseph S.M. The Role of Communication Skills in Acquiring Soft Skills for Nurses. Review of International Geographical Education Online. 2024. № 11 (10). Pp. 529-529. [https://doi.org/11\(10\):529-529-537537](https://doi.org/11(10):529-529-537537)
18. Kraja Y., Bejleri E., Saraçi P. Analyzing the Effects of Hard Skills and Soft Skills on Employment in Urban Versus Rural Communities. Journal of Management World. 2024. (4). Pp. 424-430. <https://doi.org/10.53935/jomw.v2024i4.414>
19. Sumanto E., Sassi K. Integrasi Soft Skill Dan Hard Skill: Refleksi Metode Leasson Studi Di Jepang. ULIL ALBAB Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin. 2024. № 3(11). Pp. 104-114. <https://doi.org/10.56799/jim.v3i11>
20. Sinaga J. V., Rosita S., Fitri C. The Influence of Soft Skills & Hard Skills of Students in Facing Work Readiness with Self-Efficacy as an Intervening Variable. Management Research and Behavior Journal. 2024. № 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.29103/mrbj.v4i1.14753>
21. Makarenko E.N., Evlakhova Yu.S. Study of students' ideas about soft and hard skills of a financial security specialist. Financial Research. 2024. № 25(1). Pp. 13-26. <https://doi.org/10.54220/finis.1991-0525.2024.82.1.001>
22. Nurhamidah R. The Influence of Hard Skills, Soft Skills, Spiritual Skills and Organizational Commitment on Professionalism. El-Mal Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi & Bisnis Islam. 2025. № 5. <https://doi.org/10.47467/elmal.v6i5.6440>
23. Mentari S., Nuris D. M. The Effect of Teaching Assistance on The Hard Skills and Soft Skills of Accounting Education Students. TOFEDU The Future of Education Journal. 2024. № 3 (4). Pp. 879-885. <https://doi.org/10.61445/tofedu.v3i4.168>
24. Fauziah H., Hermina T. Hard Skill of Human Resource Enhances Innovation Individual Capability at Coffee Small Medium Entreprises. Jurnal Wacana Ekonomi. 2025. № 24 (2). Pp. 073-077. <https://doi.org/10.52434/jwe.v24i2.42357>
25. Afriyeni D. The Influence of Innovation, Creativity, Hard Skills and Soft Skills on Employee Performance Sungai Penuh City Health Office. Journal of Research in Business and Management. 2024. № 12(11). Pp. 103-113. <https://doi.org/10.35629/3002-1211103113>
26. Iskhakbayeva T. Digital transformation and students' skill development: forging the balance of hard and soft skills. Bulletin of the Karaganda University Pedagogy series. 2024. № 11629 (4). Pp. 167-174. <https://doi.org/10.31489/2024ped4/167-174>
27. Васильева Т. В., Никитина Н. И., Толстикова С. Н., Вольхин С. Н. Антропологический подход в системе методологических подходов к непрерывному профессиональному образованию педагогов-психологов // Bulletin of the International Centre of Art and Education. 2023. № 6-1. С. 320-321.
28. Федеральный закон от 29 декабря 2012 г. № 273-ФЗ "Об образовании в Российской Федерации" (с изменениями и дополнениями). URL: <https://ivo.garant.ru/#/document/70291362/paragraph/1:0> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
29. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 37.03.01 Психология. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203+%/Bak/370301_B_3_23082020.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
30. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 39.03.02 Социальная работа. С изменениями и дополнениями от: 26 ноября 2020 г., 8 февраля 2021 г. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203+%/Bak/390302_B_3_15062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
31. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 44.03.01 Педагогическое образование. Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 121. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203+%/Bak/440301_B_3_15062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)

32. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 44.03.02 Психолого-педагогическое образование. Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 122. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440302_V_3_15062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
33. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 44.03.05 Педагогическое образование (с двумя профилями подготовки). Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 125. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440305_V_3_15062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
34. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 44.03.03 Специальное (дефектологическое) образование. Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 123. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440303_V_3_15062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
35. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - бакалавриат по направлению подготовки 44.03.04 Профессиональное обучение (по отраслям). Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 124. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440304_V_3_15062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
36. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования-магистратура по направлению подготовки 44.04.01 Педагогическое образование. Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 126. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440401_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
37. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - магистратура по направлению подготовки 44.04.02 Психолого-педагогическое образование. Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 127. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440402_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
38. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования-магистратура по направлению подготовки 44.04.03 Специальное (дефектологическое) образование. Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 128. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440403_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
39. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт высшего образования - магистратура по направлению подготовки 44.04.04 Профессиональное обучение (по отраслям) Утвержден приказом Министерства образования и науки Российской Федерации от 22 февраля 2018 г. № 129. URL: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440404_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
40. Профессиональный стандарт «Педагог (педагогическая деятельность в дошкольном, начальном общем, основном общем, среднем общем образовании) (воспитатель, учитель)». Утвержден приказом Министерства труда и социальной защиты Российской Федерации от 18 октября 2013 г. № 544н. URL: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.001.pdf> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
41. Профессиональный стандарт «Педагог-психолог (психолог в сфере образования)». Утвержден приказом Министерства труда и социальной защиты от 24 июля 2015 № 514 н. URL: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.002.pdf> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
42. Профессиональный стандарт «Психолог в социальной сфере», утвержден приказом Министерства труда и социальной защиты от 14 сентября 2023 г. №716 н. URL: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/03.008.pdf> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
43. Профессиональный стандарт «Специалист в области воспитания». Утвержден приказом Министерства труда и социальной защиты от 30 января 2023 №53н. URL: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.005.pdf> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
44. Профессиональный стандарт «Педагог дополнительного образования детей и взрослых», утвержден приказом Министерства труда и социальной защиты от 22 сентября 2021 г. № 652н. URL: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.003.pdf> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)
45. Профессиональный стандарт «Специалист по работе с молодежью». Утвержден приказом Министерства труда и социальной защиты от 12 февраля 2020 г. № 59н. URL: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/03.015.pdf> (дата обращения: 30.04.25)

REFERENCES

1. Education for sustainable development: a roadmap (2022). Corporate author: UNESCO [66654]. Paris 07 SP, France. – Document code: 10.54675/YFRE1448, 66 p. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374802>
2. Novikova N. V., Nechaeva T. Yu., Avezova, Dubrovina I. A. The humanization of medical education: publication review. *Problems of Social Hygiene Public and History of Medicine*, 2024, July, no. 32 (4), pp.

- 828-832. DOI: 10.32687/0869-866X-2024-32-4-828-832
3. Soares F., Lopes A. Fostering humanization in education: a scoping review on mindfulness and teacher education. *Frontiers in Education*, 2024, no. 9. DOI: 10.3389/educ.2024.1373500
 4. Rodriguez M.E., Fortunato I. Paulo Friere's contributions to 21st century teacher education: Inspirations for (re)discovering humanization. *Policy Futures in Education*, 2025, February. DOI: 10.1177/14782103251323403
 5. Dorathy W.C., Sam-Eleyi F.O. Workplace Humanization and Job Effectiveness of Business Education Graduates in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State. *Journal of Advances in Education and Philosophy*, 2024, no. 8 (09), pp. 544-551. DOI:10.36348/jaep.2024.v08i09.004
 6. Azuakor P.O. The role of religion (Islam and Christianity) and education for humanization: Nigeria in perspective. *Integrity Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 2023, no. 4 (1), pp. 7-15. DOI: 10.31248/IJAH2022.065
 7. Lyubtsova A. V. Value orientations of modern youth in the context of the formation of prosocial behavior. *Russian Psychological Journal*, 2020, vol. 17, no. 4, p. 65-79.
 8. Kalinina T. V., Guseva N. V. Formation of prosocial behavior in the context of professional training of students of helping specialties and areas of study. *Social and psychological problems of prosocial behavior of the modern generation of children and youth. Materials of the II All-Russian scientific and practical conference with international participation*. Simferopol, OOO "Izdatelstvo Tipografiya "Arial", pp. 35-44.
 9. Shmeleva E. A., Basimov M. M., Kislyakov P. A., Konstantinova N. P. Psychological prerequisites for motivating prosocial activity of student youth. *Scientific notes of the Russian State Social University*, 2021, vol. 20, no. 1 (158), pp. 5-15.
 10. Shmeleva E. A., Kislyakov P. A., Starodubtseva L. V., Priyatkina N. Yu. Prosocial activity of future teachers. *Bulletin of the Mininsk University*, 2021, vol. 9, no 4, pp. 1-20.
 11. Tarasova E. O., Yuryev K. V. Social and psychological portrait of a socially active student of a technical university. *Bulletin of the Samara State Technical University. Series: Psychological and pedagogical sciences*, 2015, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 206-210.
 12. Shmeleva E. A., Okeanskaya Zh. L., Kislyakov P. A. Methodology for studying the prosocial activity of students of educational organizations of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of Russia. *Fire and emergency safety*, 2020, no. 3 (18), pp. 70-81.
 13. Toropov P. B. Result of the pedagogical experiment: social assistance as a technology of prosocial education. *Bulletin of the Baltic State Academy of the Fishing Fleet*, 2018, no. 1 (43), pp. 98-103.
 14. Eroshenkova E. I., Shapovalova I. S., Karabutova E. A., Anokhina S. V., Miroshnikova O. S. Prosocial competence model of the future teacher. *Education and Science*, 2022, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 11-47. DOI: 10.17853/1994-5639-2022-2-11-47
 15. Bhaskar C. V., Priyadharshini P. R. S., Govindharaj P., Sam D Pr. The role of group projects in enhancing soft skills. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 2025, no. 12(1), pp. 1-9. DOI: 10.1057/s41599-025-04807-x
 16. Nikitina E. A., Budovskaya I. V. The empirical research of development features of students' soft-skills. *Proceedings of the Southwest State University Series Linguistics and Pedagogy*, 2025, no. 14(4), pp. 121-131. DOI: 10.21869/2223-151X-2024-14-4-121-131
 17. Ayyadurai S., Akkara Joy S., Edapallikunnel J.J., Joseph S.M. The Role of Communication Skills in Acquiring Soft Skills for Nurses. *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, 2024, no. 11 (10), pp. 529-529. DOI: 11(10):529- 529-537537
 18. Kraja Y., Bejleri E., Saraçi P. Analyzing the Effects of Hard Skills and Soft Skills on Employment in Urban Versus Rural Communities. *Journal of Management World*, 2024, no. 4, pp. 424-430. DOI: 10.53935/jomw.v2024i4.414
 19. Sumanto E., Sassi K. Integrasi Soft Skill Dan Hard Skill: Refleksi Metode Leasson Studi Di Jepang. *ULIL ALBAB Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin*, 2024, no. 3 (11), pp. 104-114. DOI: 10.56799/jim.v3i11
 20. Sinaga J. V., Rosita S., Fitri C. The Influence of Soft Skills & Hard Skills of Students in Facing Work Readiness with Self-Efficacy as an Intervening Variable. *Management Research and Behavior Journal*, 2024, no. 4 (1). DOI: 10.29103/mrbj.v4i1.14753
 21. Makarenko E.N., Evlakhova Yu.S. Study of students' ideas about soft and hard skills of a financial security specialist. *Financial Research*, 2024, no. 25 (1), pp. 13-26. DOI: 10.54220/finis.1991-0525.2024.82.1.001
 22. Nurhamidah R. The Influence of Hard Skills, Soft Skills, Spiritual Skills and Organizational Commitment on Professionalism. *El-Mal Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi & Bisnis Islam*, 2025, no. 6 (5). DOI: 10.47467/elmal.v6i5.6440
 23. Mentari S., Nuris D. M. The Effect of Teaching Assistance on The Hard Skills and Soft Skills of Accounting Education Students. *TOFEDU The Future of Education Journal*, 2024, no. 3(4), pp. 879-885. DOI: 10.61445/tofedu.v3i4.168
 24. Fauziah H., Hermina T. Hard Skill of Human Resource Enhances Innovation Individual Capability at Coffee Small Medium Entreprises. *Jurnal Wacana Ekonomi*, 2025 no. 24(2), pp. 073-077. DOI: 10.52434/jwe.v24i2.42357
 25. Afriyeni D. The Influence of Innovation, Creativity, Hard Skills and Soft Skills on Employee Performance Sungai Penuh City Health Office. *Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 2024, no. 12(11), pp.

- 103-113. DOI: 10.35629/3002-1211103113
26. Iskhakbayeva T. Digital transformation and students' skill development: forging the balance of hard and soft skills. *Bulletin of the Karaganda University Pedagogy series*, 2024, no. 11629(4), pp. 167-174. DOI: 10.31489/2024ped4/167-174
 27. Vasilyeva T. V., Nikitina N. I., Tolstikova S. N., Volkhin S. N. Anthropological approach in the system of methodological approaches to continuous professional education of educational psychologists. *Bulletin of the International Centre of Art and Education*, 2023, no. 6-1, pp. 320-321.
 28. Federal Law of December 29, 2012 No. 273-FZ "On Education in the Russian Federation" (with amendments and additions). Available at: <https://ivo.garant.ru/#/document/70291362/paragraph/1:0> (accessed 30 April 2025)
 29. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 37.03.01 Psychology. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/370301_B_3_23082020.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 30. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 39.03.02 Social work. With amendments and additions from: November 26, 2020, February 8, 2021. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/390302_B_3_15062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 31. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 44.03.01 Pedagogical education. Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 121. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440301_B_3_15062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 32. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 44.03.02 Psychological and pedagogical education. Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 122. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440302_B_3_15062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 33. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 44.03.05 Pedagogical education (with two training profiles). Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 N 125. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440305_B_3_15062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 34. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 44.03.03 Special (defectological) education Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 N 123. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440303_B_3_15062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 35. Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the field of training 44.03.04 Professional training (by industry). Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 124. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Bak/440304_B_3_15062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 36. Federal state educational standard of higher education - master's degree in the field of training 44.04.01 Pedagogical education. Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 126. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440401_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 37. Federal state educational standard of higher education - master's degree in the field of training 44.04.02 Psychological and pedagogical education. Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 127. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440402_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 38. Federal state educational standard of higher education - master's degree in the field of training 44.04.03 Special (defectological) education. Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 128. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440403_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 39. Federal state educational standard of higher education - Master's degree in the field of training 44.04.04 Professional training (by industry) Approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated February 22, 2018 No. 129. Available at: https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/FGOS%20VO%203++/Mag/440404_%D0%9C_3_17062021.pdf (accessed 30 April 2025)
 40. Professional standard "Teacher (teaching activity in preschool, primary general, basic general, secondary general education) (educator, teacher)". Approved by the order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation dated October 18, 2013 No. 544n. Available at: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.001.pdf> (accessed 30 April 2025)
 41. Professional standard "Teacher-psychologist (psychologist in the field of education)". Approved by the order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection dated July 24, 2015 No. 514 n. Available at: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.002.pdf> (accessed 30 April 2025)
 42. Professional standard "Psychologist in the social sphere", approved by the order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection dated September 14, 2023 No. 716 n. Available at: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/03.008.pdf> (accessed 30 April 2025)
 43. Professional standard "Specialist in the field of education". Approved by the order of the Ministry of Labor

and Social Protection dated January 30, 2023. No. 53n. Available at: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles//profstandart/01> (accessed 30 April 2025)

44. Professional standard "Teacher of additional education for children and adults", approved by order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection dated September 22, 2021 No. 652n. Available at: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/01.003.pdf> (accessed 30 April 2025)
45. Professional standard "Youth Work Specialist". Approved by order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection dated February 12, 2020 No. 59n. Available at: <https://fgosvo.ru/uploadfiles/profstandart/03.015.pdf> (accessed 30 April 2025)

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